

AN OVERVIEW ON THE SUBFAMILY CREMASTINAE FÖRSTER, 1869 (HYMENOPTERA: ICHNEUMONIDAE) FROM TURKEY

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Abstract

Fauna of the subfamily Cremastinae Förster, 1869 (Ichneumonidae: Hymenoptera) on the territory of Turkey was investigated. The survey was conducted during the period 1995-2020. A total of 54 species belonging to eight genera have been listed. Among the material collected in the past 25 years, the species *Cremastus brevicornis* Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999; *C. kasparyani* Kolarov Gürbüz & Birol, 2014; *C. petiolaris* Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999; *C. tristator* Aubert, 1970; *Nothocremastus beyarslani* Kolarov, 1997 and *Temelucha turcata* Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999 were listed as endemic to the investigated territory. Additionally, a male of *Eucremastus priebei* Kolarov, 1999 is recorded for the first time from Turkey. Turkish species of the subfamily Cremastinae have been analyzed according to biogeographical and zoogeographical features.

KEY WORDS: Cremastinae, diversity, survey, Turkey

Introduction

Hymenoptera is one of the four largest orders of insects, with over 152,677 described species in the world (Aguiar *et al.*, 2013). They are found all over the world but are more abundant and diverse in tropical and temperate regions. Ichneumonidae is the biggest hymenopteran family with 1,601 genera and 25,285 described species (Yu *et al.*, 2016).

Turkey has rich faunistic and floristic features due to its geographic and topographic position. After 1995, many studies (Çoruh, 2017; Kolarov *et al.*, 2017; Narmanlıoğlu & Çoruh, 2017; Çoruh *et al.*, 2018; Sarı & Çoruh, 2018; Riedel *et al.*, 2018; Çoruh, 2019a,b; Çoruh *et al.*, 2019; Özdan & Gürbüz, 2019; Çaylak, 2019; Çaylak & Çoruh, 2020 a,b; Kolarov *et al.*, 2020; Kırac & Gürbüz, 2020; Kolarov *et al.*, 2021; Yurtcan *et al.*, 2021) have been done on the Ichneumonidae family, but it is still inadequate, since many of these studies were carried out in Eastern Anatolia, Marmara and the Mediterranean regions. Research in other regions of

Turkey is scarce. Today, Ichneumonidae species in Turkey number 1,309 species from 289 genera (Teymuroğlu & Çoruh, 2021; Kolarov *et al.*, 2021, Yurtcan *et al.* 2021).

The subfamily Cremastinae is a moderately large subfamily in the family Ichneumonidae and contains about 828 described species in 35 genera from throughout the world (Yu *et al.*, 2016). Cremastinae occur mainly in arid regions (Amiri *et al.*, 2019). Cremastines are distinguished from other Ichneumonidae by a sclerotized bridge separating the membranous sockets of the tibial spurs and the basitarsus of all tibiae (Townes, 1958). The Cremastinae, along with the subfamilies Campopleginae Foerster, 1869, Tersilochinae Schmiedeknecht, 1910, Anomaloninae Viereck, 1918, and Ophioninae Shuckard, 1840, are included in the so-called "ophionoid complex". Inclusion is broadly based on common similarities among the mentioned groups. Usually, Cremastinae can be distinguished from other members of the "ophionoid complex" with the naked eye because of certain specific features: the slender body and legs, small head, the long, thin and straight ovipositor and the "tender" wings (Narolsky, 2002).

Cremastinae of Turkey was investigated up to 1995 by several researchers (Kohl, 1905; Schmiedeknecht, 1908; Altay, 1966; Thompson, 1957; Sedivy, 1959, Aubert, 1970; Sedivy, 1971; Tuatay *et al.*, 1972; Aubert; 1977; Soydanbay, 1978; Aubert 1981; Doğanlar, 1987; Horstmann, 1990; Özdemir & Kılınçer, 1990; Öncüer, 1991; Kolarov, 1992). Kolarov (1995) prepared a catalogue of the Turkish Ichneumonidae. In this catalogue, the subfamily Cremastinae is represented by 5 genera and 11 species. Today, this number has reached 8 genera and 54 species (Kolarov, 1997, 2007, 2016; Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999; Kolarov *et al.*, 2002a,b, 2014, 2016, 2017; Kolarov & Yurtcan, 2009; Kolarov & Çalmaşur, 2011; Çoruh *et al.*, 2013; 2014; Çoruh & Kolarov, 2016; Pekel, 1998; Pekel (Çoruh) & Özbek, 2000; Narolsky, 2001; Özdemir & Özdemir, 2002; Gürbüz, 2005; Gürbüz & Aksoylar, 2005; Beyarslan *et al.*, 2006; Anlaş *et al.*, 2009; Eroğlu *et al.*, 2011; Özdan, 2014; Özdan & Gürbüz, 2016; Sarı & Çoruh, 2018).

Our aim was to provide the first comprehensive and validated species list of the subfamily Cremastinae in Turkey. The list is based on both an extensive literature research and a review of all reliably identified specimens present in the Entomological Museum, Erzurum, Turkey (EMET).

Materials and Methods

The subfamily Cremastinae from Anatolia was systematically studied in various biotopes between 1995-2020. The research area is shown in the Fig. 1. Furthermore, some samples collected before 1995 were also evaluated. Sampling was mostly carried out with an entomological sweep net on flowering plants and a Malaise trap was also used. Collected samples were placed in 70% alcohol and brought to the laboratory. All specimens were pinned and labelled and thus prepared for identification.

The samples collected by different researchers before 1995 have been added. All taxa in tables are listed in alphabetical order. Distribution of species in Turkey and the world is taken from the Catalogue of World Ichneumonidae (Yu *et al.*, 2016). Different data on the species are summarized in the tables.

Figure 1. Study area. Geographical regions: Aegean Region (AR), Black Sea Region (BSR), Central Anatolia Region (CAR), Eastern Anatolia Region (EAR), Marmara Region (MR), Mediterranean Region (MtR), Southeastern Anatolia (SAR).

Results and Discussion

A total of 54 species belonging to eight genera from the subfamily Cremastinae are presented and discussed (Table I).

The species belong to the following genera: *Cremastus* Gravenhorst, 1829; *Dimophora* Förster, 1869; *Eucremastoides* Kolarov, 1980; *Eucremastus* Szépligeti, 1905; *Nothocremastus* Dasch, 1979; *Pristomerus* Curtis, 1836; *Trathala* Cameron, 1899 and *Temelucha* Förster, 1869.

A total of 424 samples are available in the EMET. Regarding the distribution of species according to genus, 14 species and 53 samples belong to the genus *Cremastus*, two species and nine samples to the genus *Dimophora*, one species and three samples to the genus *Eucremastoides*, three species and two samples to the genus *Eucremastus*, one species and two samples to *Nothocremastus*, nine species and 91 samples to *Pristomerus*, one species and 17 samples to *Trathala*, 23 species and 247 samples to *Temelucha*.

It is obvious that *Temelucha* is the richest genus for both species and samples according to presented genera in Table I, whereas *Cremastus* is the most numerous species in the world (Yu *et al.*, 2016).

Table I. Data of collected species: Individual numbers (IN), vertical distribution (VD), seasonal dynamics (SD), geographical regions (GR), zoogeographical regions (ZR), first record of Turkey (FRT) of specimens. Vertical distribution (VD) (in meters above sea level): A: 0-500 m, B: 501-750 m, C: 751-1000 m, D: 1001-1250 m, E: 1251- 1500 m, F: 1501-1750 m, G: 1751-2000 m, H: 2001-2500 m. Seasonal dynamics (SD): Ap: April, M: May, J: June, Jl: July, Aug: August, S: September. Geographical regions are displayed in Fig. 1. Zoogeographical regions (ZR): AFR: Afrotropical Region, E: Europe, EP: Eastern Palaearctic, NEAR: Nearctic Region, OCN: Oceanic; ORR: Oriental, WP: Western Palearctic.

Names of Taxa	IN	VD	SD	GR	ZR	FRT
<i>Creomastus aegyptiacus</i> Szépligeti, 1905	1	A	Ap	MtR	E, WP	Çoruh <i>et al.</i> , 2013
<i>Creomastus bellicosus</i> Gravenhorst, 1829	8	F	Jl	EAR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Creomastus brevicornis</i> Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999	1	D	Jl	CAR	WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Creomastus crassicornis</i> Thomson, 1880	1	H	Aug	MtR	E, WP	Sedivy, 1959
<i>Creomastus geminus</i> Gravenhorst, 1829	4	A, H	J, Jl	EAR, MR	AFR, EP, E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Creomastus gigas</i> Heinrich, 1953	2	G, H	J, Jl	EAR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov <i>et al.</i> , 2002b
<i>Creomastus inflatipes</i> Roman, 1939	4	A	?	MR	E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Creomastus kasparyani</i> Kolarov, Gürbüz & Birol, 2014	1	D	J	MtR	WP	Kolarov <i>et al.</i> , 2014
<i>Creomastus lineatus</i> Gravenhorst, 1829	3	A	Ap, J	AR, MtR	E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Creomastus petiolaris</i> Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999	1	B	S	MtR	WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Creomastus puberulus</i> (Szépligeti, 1899)	9	E	J	EAR	E, WP	Kolarov & Yurtcan, 2009
<i>Creomastus pungens</i> Gravenhorst, 1829	12	A, E, F, H	Ap, M, J, Jl, Aug	AR, CAR, EAR, MR, MtR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov, 1997
<i>Creomastus spectator</i> Gravenhorst, 1829	2	A, B	M, Aug	MR, MtR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov, 1997
<i>Creomastus tristator</i> Aubert, 1970	4	E	M, J, Jl, Aug	Anatolia, MtR	WP	Aubert, 1970
<i>Dimophora nitens</i> (Gravenhorst, 1829)	4	A, B, D	M, S	CAR, MR, MtR	AUS, EP, E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Dimophora robusta</i> Brischke, 1880	5	E, F, G	J, Jl	EAR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov <i>et al.</i> , 2002b
<i>Eucremastoides angelovi</i> Kolarov, 1980	3	F, G, H	Jl, Jl	EAR, BSR	E, WP	Kolarov, 1992
<i>Eucremastus collaris</i> Narolsky, 1990	2	A, F	M, J	AR, EAR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Eucremastus priebei</i> Kolarov, 1999	1	E	M	EAR	E, WP	Kolarov <i>et al.</i> , 2002b
<i>Nothocremastus beyarslanii</i> Kolarov, 1997	2	A, B	M	MtR, SAR	WP	Kolarov, 1997
<i>Pristomerus armatus</i> Lucas, 1894	44	A, D, E, F, G, H	M, J, Jl, Aug	CAR, EAR, MtR	EP, E, WP	Horstmann, 1990
<i>Pristomerus hebraicator</i> Aubert, 1979	1	D	J	MtR	WP	Çoruh <i>et al.</i> , 2013
<i>Pristomerus luridus</i> Kokujev, 1905	2	F	S	EAR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov, 2007
<i>Pristomerus kasparyani</i> Narolsky, 1886	1	D	M	AR	E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Pristomerus mesopotamicus</i> Horstmann, 1990	1	C	Jl	CAR	E, WP	Kolarov & Yurtcan, 2009
<i>Pristomerus orbitalis</i> Holmgren, 1860	2	G	Aug	EAR	EP, E, NEAR, WP	Kolarov, 2016
<i>Pristomerus pallidus</i> Thomson, 1890	4	D, H	M, Jl	EAR, MtR	EP, E, WP	Pekel, 1998

Table I – continued

Names of Taxa	IN	VD	SD	GR	ZR	FRT
<i>Pristomerus rivalis</i> Narolsky, 1987	7	F, H	Jl, Aug	EAR	EP, E, WP	Pekel (Çoruh) & Özbek, 2000
<i>Pristomerus vulnerator</i> (Panzer, 1799)	29	A, B, C, E, F, H	Ap, M, J, Jl, Aug	BSR, CAR, EAR, MR, MtR	EP, E, NEAR, OCN, ORR, WP	Kohl, 1905
<i>Trathala hierochontica</i> (Schmiedeknecht, 1910)	17	A, B, D, E	J, Jl, S	EAR, MR, MtR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Temelucha albipennis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	2	E	J	EAR	E, WP	Kolarov & Yurtcan, 2009
<i>Temelucha anatolica</i> (Sedivy, 1959)	13	A, G	J, Jl, Aug, S	AR, EAR, MtR	EP, E, WP	Sedivy, 1971
<i>Temelucha annulata</i> (Szépligeti, 1899)	7	A, G	J, Jl, Aug	EAR, MR	E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Temelucha arenosa</i> (Szépligeti, 1899)	24	A, D, F, G, H	M, J, Jl, Aug	AR, EAR, MtR, SAR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Temelucha brevipetiolata</i> Kolarov, 1989	3	A	J	MR	E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Temelucha caudata</i> (Szépligeti, 1900)	9	A, E, G, H	Ap, J, Jl	EAR, MR, MtR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Temelucha confluens</i> (Gravenhorst, 1829)	6	D, E	M, J, Jl, Aug	CAR, EAR	E, WP	Kohl, 1905
<i>Temelucha decorata</i> (Gravenhorst, 1829)	17	A, D, F, G, H	J, Jl, Aug, S	CAR, EAR, MtR, MR	EP, E, NEAR, WP	Thompson, 1957
<i>Temelucha discoidalis</i> (Szépligeti, 1899)	11	A, C, D, F, G	Ap, J, Jl, Aug	CAR, EAR, MtR	EP, E, WP	Pekel, 1998
<i>Temelucha genalis</i> (Szépligeti, 1900)	11	A, D, E	M, J, Jl	EAR, MR, MtR	E, WP	Kolarov <i>et al.</i> , 1997
<i>Temelucha guttifer</i> (Thomson, 1896)	1	A	Aug	MtR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov, 1997
<i>Temelucha interruptor</i> (Gravenhorst, 1829)	28	A, D, G, F, H	J, Jl, Aug	CAR, EAR, MR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov <i>et al.</i> , 1997
<i>Temelucha lucida</i> (Szépligeti, 1900)	7	E, H	M, Jl, Aug	AR, CAR, EAR	EP, E, WP	Pekel, 1998
<i>Temelucha meridiionellator</i> Aubert, 1981	4	A, H	M, Ap, J,	EAR, SAR	E, WP	Aubert, 1981
<i>Temelucha observator</i> Aubert, 1966	7	A	M, J	AR	EP, E, WP	Aubert, 1977
<i>Temelucha ophthalmica</i> (Holmgren, 1858)	2	A	Aug	MR	E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Temelucha pseudocaudata</i> Kolarov, 1982	5	F	Jl	EAR	E, WP	Pekel (Çoruh) & Özbek, 2000
<i>Temelucha signata</i> (Holmgren, 1860)	2	D	S	CAR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Temelucha schoenobia</i> (Thomson, 1890)	21	A, D, E	J, Jl, Aug, S	AR, MtR, SAR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Temelucha tricolorata</i> Sedivy, 1968	8	A, D, E	Ap, J, Jl	CAR, MtR, SAR	E, WP	Gürbüz & Aksoylar, 2005
<i>Temelucha tuberculata</i> Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999	1	D	?	EAR	NEAR	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Temelucha turcata</i> Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999	54	A, B, C, D, E, F	Ap, M, J, Jl	CAR, EAR, MR, MtR, SAR	WP	Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999
<i>Temelucha variipes</i> (Szépligeti, 1900)	4	A, G, H	J, Jl, Aug	EAR, MtR	EP, E, WP	Kolarov, 1997

Table II. Parasitoid species found on hosts.

Parasitoid	Host	References
<i>Pristomerus vulnerator</i>	<i>Archips</i> sp. (Tortricidae)	Özdemir & Özdemir, 2002
	<i>Cydia molesta</i> Busck (Tortricidae)	Altay, 1966; Tuatay et al. 1972; Öncüer, 1991
	<i>Cydia pomelle</i> L. (Tortricidae)	Altay, 1966; Gürses et al., 1985; Önder & Zümreoğlu 1985; Soydanbay, 1978; Öncüer, 1991
	<i>Gypsonoma dealbana</i> Frölich (Tortricidae)	Tuatay et al., 1972; Soydanbay, 1978; Doğanlar, 1987; Özdemir & Kılıncıer, 1991
	<i>Hedya nubiferana</i> Haworth (Tortricidae)	Doğanlar, 1987
	<i>Nordmannia acaciae</i> F. (Lycaenidae)	Bolu et al., 2007
<i>Temelucha decorata</i>	<i>Scrobipalpa ocellatella</i> Boyd. (Gelechiidae)	Öncüer, 1991
	<i>Spodoptera exigua</i> Hübner (Noctuidae)	Kolarov, 1995

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ПРЕГЛЕД ВРСТА ПОТФАМИЛИЈЕ CREMASTINAE FÖRSTER, 1869 (HYMENOPTERA: ICHNEUMONIDAE) У ТУРСКОЈ

САЛИХА ЧОРУХ

Извод

Истражена је фауна потфамилије Cremastinae Förster, 1869 (Ichneumonidae: Hymenoptera) на територији Турске. Истраживање је спроведено у периоду 1995-2020. Забележене су укупно 54 врсте из осам родова. Међу материјалом прикупљеним у последњих 25 година, врсте *Cremastus brevicornis* Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999; *C. kasparyani* Kolarov Gürbüz & Birol, 2014; *C. petiolaris* Kolarov & Beyarslan; 1999; *C. tristator* Aubert, 1970; *Nothocremastus beyarslani* Kolarov, 1997 и *Temelucha turcata* Kolarov & Beyarslan, 1999 су ендемичне за истражену територију. Поред тога, први пут је забележен мужјак *Eucremastus priebei* Kolarov, 1999 из Турске. Врсте потфамилије Cremastinae анализирани су према биогеографским и зоогеографским карактеристикама.

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